

Stereochemical Features of Some Ni(II) and Co(II) Complexes of N-2, 5-Dihydroxy Acetophenacylidene Anthranilic Acid

P SINGH, V SINGH, R PAL and R L GOEL

Department of Chemistry S S V College Hapur India

Manuscript received 9 November 1976 accepted 3 August 1977

Nickel(II) and Cobalt(II) Complexes of the Composition $H_2[M(L)_2]$ and $H[M(L)X(H_2O)_2]$ [L=N-2, 5-dihydroxyacetophenacylideneanthranilic acid, X=Br] have been isolated and characterised by elemental analyses, magnetic, conductometric, electronic and IR spectral studies. Electronic spectral studies indicate that the latter type of complexes are tetragonally distorted from their regular cubic symmetry and it has been concluded that this distortion is produced due to unequal donor strengths of H_2O ligand. A possible correlation of it has been sought with the low values of magnetic moments observed in the complexes. IR spectral studies show that the metals are coordinated through the nitrogen of azomethine group, oxygens of carboxylic and phenolic groups. The entrance of water molecules within the coordination sphere is also supported by IR spectral studies.

SCHIFF Bases are very good chelating agents and their complexes with transition metals have recently been studied by workers¹⁻⁴. N-2, 5-dihydroxyacetophenacylideneanthranilic acid (abbreviated as H_3 -DAPAA) is capable of chelation by means of nitrogen atom of azomethine and oxygen atoms of carboxylic and phenolic groups. It was therefore decided to isolate a variety of Ni(II) and Co(II) complexes of H_3 -DAPAA with common anions in nonaqueous media and investigate the possible bonding through IR spectral studies. We have also demonstrated the effect of distortion from the regular octahedral structure produced by H_2O ligand of unequal donor strength on the electronic spectra of complexes.

Experimental

N-2, 5-dihydroxyacetophenacylideneanthranilic acid was prepared by refluxing equimolar quantities of 2, 5-dihydroxyacetophenone and anthranilic acid in ethanol for 4.5 hrs. The contents were cooled, filtered and the product was washed with solvent ether (b.p. 60-80°). It was purified by crystallising from ethanol and its 80 per cent solution was used throughout.

Preparation and isolation of complexes

(a) Dihydrogen-bis (N-2, 5-dihydroxyacetophenacylideneanthranilic acid) Ni(II)

A yellow-ochre solution was obtained by adding 7.5 ml of 0.02M ethanolic solution of nickel chloride to 30.0 ml of an equimolar solution of H_3 -DAPAA at pH ~ 4.0. The reaction mixture was refluxed on steam bath for 3.5 hrs and the contents were cooled and kept in a refrigerator for two days, when yellowish green crystals were settled. The crystals were washed with water, ethanol and finally with

ether and dried in vacuum at room temperature (yield 80 per cent). Anal. Calcd for $H_2[Ni(C_{15}H_{11}NO_4)_2]$ C, 60.10, H, 4.0, N, 4.66, Ni, 9.84 per cent. Found C, 59.85, H, 3.80, N, 4.54, Ni, 9.76 per cent.

(b) Monobromo-monohydrogen mono (N-2, 5-dihydroxyacetophenacylideneanthranilic acid) diaquo Ni(II)

A yellow coloured solution was obtained by mixing equimolar 50 per cent ethanolic solutions of nickel bromide and the ligand in the stoichiometric ratio (1:1). The reaction mixture was concentrated and the concentrate was kept in a refrigerator for few days, when yellow coloured crystals were separated out (yield 70 per cent). It is soluble in DMF, DMSO, nitromethane, nitrobenzene and benzene. Anal. Calcd for $H[Ni(C_{15}H_{11}NO_4)Br(H_2O)_2]$ C, 45.03, H, 3.75, N, 3.50, Br, 20.01, Ni, 14.69 per cent. Found C, 44.88, H, 3.52, N, 3.20, Br, 19.65, Ni, 14.54 per cent.

(c) Dihydrogen-bis (N-2, 5-dihydroxyacetophenacylideneanthranilic acid) Co(II)

25 ml of 0.03M acetic solution of cobalt chloride were mixed with 50 ml of equimolar acetic solution of the ligand. The reaction mixture was placed in vacuum desiccator over fused calcium chloride and concentrated by evaporation. The concentrate was cooled in refrigerator for few days, red coloured crystals were deposited which were washed successively with water, ethanol and ether and dried in vacuum. The complex compound is soluble in DMF, benzene, acetone, nitromethane (NM) and dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO). Anal. Calcd for $H_2[Co(C_{15}H_{11}NO_4)_2]$ C, 60.10, H, 4.0, N, 4.67, Co, 9.83 per cent. Found C, 59.88, H, 3.88, N, 4.52, Co, 9.67 per cent.

(d) *Monohydrogen-monobromo mono-(N-2 5-dihydroxyacetophenacylideneanthranilic acido) diaquo Co (II)*

Presence of hydrogen ions in the complexes was shown as reported previously ⁵

Analyses and apparatus

The microanalyses of carbon hydrogen, nitrogen and halogens were performed by Mr A H Siddiqui, Indian Institute of Technology, Kanpur-16, India. The conductometric, magnetic electronic and i r spectral measurements were made as reported previously ^{4 5}. Table 1 represents the magnetic, thermal and conductivity data of the complexes. The ligand field parameters are cited in Table 2. Tentative assignments of the bands observed in the i r spectra of H₃-DAPAA and its complexes are given in Table 3.

Equimolar 75 per cent ethanolic solutions (0.02M) of Cobalt(II) bromide and the ligand were mixed in stoichiometric ratio (1:1). The contents were refluxed on waterbath for 2.5 hrs and cooled, when brown-green coloured crystals of the complex separated out. The crystals were washed with water and ethanol and dried yield 85 per cent. It is soluble in DMF, NM, DMSO and benzene. Anal. Calcd for H[Co(C₁₅H₁₁NO₄)₂Br(H₂O)₂]: C 45.0, H 3.80, N 3.50, Br 20.01, Co 14.70 per cent. Found: C, 44.62, H 3.61, N 3.38, Br, 19.20, Co, 14.35 per cent.

TABLE 1—MAGNETIC MOMENT, THERMAL AND CONDUCTIVITY DATA

Compound	Temp (°K)	X _M × 10 ⁶ (cgs units)	μ _{eff} (BM)	MP (°C)	Δ _M (DMF)	Δ _M (NM)
H ₂ [Ni(C ₁₅ H ₁₁ NO ₄) ₂] (a)	303	3683	3.0	200	142	156
H[Ni(C ₁₅ H ₁₁ NO ₄) ₂ Br(H ₂ O) ₂] (b)	303	3665	2.70	310	80	75
H ₂ [Co(C ₁₅ H ₁₁ NO ₄) ₂] (c)	303	10640	4.82	255	156	170
H[Co(C ₁₅ H ₁₁ NO ₄) ₂ Br(H ₂ O) ₂] (d)	303	7138	4.12	286	85	90

Δ_M molecular conductance in ohm⁻¹ mole⁻¹ cm² at 25°

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA AND LIGAND FIELD PARAMETERS OF Ni(II) AND Co(II) COMPLEXES (VALUES IN CM⁻¹)

Compound	Observed bands and their assignments			Calculated band positions		[(ν ₂ - ν ₃) calcd (ν ₃ - ν ₂) obs]	ν ₂ ν ₁	B	Dt	D _q (x y)	D _q (z)
	³ A _{2g} (F) →	³ T _{2g} (F) (ν ₁)	³ T _{1g} (F) (ν ₂)	³ T _{1g} (P) (ν ₃)	ν ₂						
H ₂ [Ni(C ₁₅ H ₁₁ NO ₄) ₂]	9000	15000	26500	14955	26545	90	1.66	966	—	—	—
H[Ni(C ₁₅ H ₁₁ NO ₄) ₂ Br(H ₂ O) ₂]	10900 12640	20000	30200	19100	32090	2790	1.83	1166	+193	1264	174
	⁴ T _{1g} (F) →			⁴ T _{2g} (F) (ν ₁)		⁴ A _{2g} (F) (ν ₂)	⁴ T _{1g} (P) (ν ₃)	ν ₂	10D _q	B	β
H ₂ [Co(C ₁₅ H ₁₁ NO ₄) ₂]	9000	20000	25000	20900	10530	1097	0.98				
H[Co(C ₁₅ H ₁₁ NO ₄) ₂ Br(H ₂ O) ₂]	8300	17350	23650	17560	9500	786	0.81				

TABLE 3 INFRARED SPECTRAL DATA (VALUES IN cm^{-1})

Ligand	Complex (a)	Complex (b)	Complex (c)	Complex (d)	Tentative assignments
1630 (m)	1610 (m)	1620 (m)	1610 (m)	1620 (m)	C=C stretching
3000 (w)	3000 (w)	2990 (w)	3000 (w)	2990 (w)	C-H aromatic
1610 (s)	1600 (s)	1600 (s)	1600 (s)	1640 (s)	Aromatic phenyl ring
2820 (w)	2810 (w)	2800 (w)	2820 (w)	2830 (w)	-CH stretching in CH_2
1600 (s)	1490 (s)	1490 (s)	1550 (s)	1500 (s)	-C=N perturbed
3440 (sh)	3350 (sh)	3380 (sh)	3400 (sh)	3400 (sh)	-OH phenolic (Reactive)
3280 (s)	3280 (s)	3270 (s)	3275 (s)	3280 (s)	-OH phenolic (Unreactive)
2570 (w)	2490 (w)	2490 (w)	2500 (w)	2500 (w)	-OH carboxylic
—	478 (w)	475 (m)	460 (m)	470 (w)	(M-O)
—	500 (m)	490 (m)	500 (m)	515 (m)	(M-N)
—	—	350 (w)	—	360 (w)	(M-Br)
—	—	3300 (sh)	—	3325 (sh)	(H_2O) stretching

m=medium, w=weak, s=sharp and sh=shoulder

Results And Discussion

Analytical results show 1:1 and 1:2 metal to ligand stoichiometric ratio for Ni(II) and Co(II) complexes. The complexes were insoluble in water but soluble in DMF, DMSO, nitrobenzene and nitromethane (NM). The complexes show uni-univalent and biunivalent electrolytic nature as revealed by the molecular conductance data $75-90 \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ mole}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$ and $142-170 \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ mole}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$ respectively^{6,7}. The acidic nature of the complexes was noticed by neutralising with caustic soda, 1 and 2g equivalents were used for complete neutralisation of uni-univalent and biunivalent complexes respectively⁸.

Ni(II) Complexes

Ni(II) having electronic configuration $3d^8$ should exhibit magnetic moment higher than that expected for two unpaired electrons in octahedral symmetry (2.80-3.42 B.M.) The magnetic moment value (3.0 B.M.) observed for the complex $\text{H}_2[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}_4)_2]$ is comparable with the assignment of octahedral configuration. If in case of Ni(II), symmetry is allowed to be lower than cubic and if low symmetry component is larger, then spin paired term may be found in the neighbourhood⁸. Recently Holt and others⁹ have shown that some complexes of Ni(II) lie on broadline between spin-free and spin-paired behaviour. At low temperatures it reaches diamagnetism whilst as the temperature increases, the magnetic moment approaches the spin-free value. X-ray investigation^{10,11} of paramagnetic (2.58 B.M.) bis-(mesostilbenediamine) nickel(II) dichloroacetate, has shown that crystal of this complex consists of a mixture of paramagnetic octahedral molecules and diamagnetic planar molecules. The subnormal magnetic moment 2.70 B.M. observed for $\text{H}[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}_4)\text{Br}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ complex may be assumed to be intermediate between that of the low spin state (0.5 B.M. due to residual paramagnetism) and the high spin state (2.8-3.82 B.M.). It appears that the energy difference between the singlet and triplet has become comparable with the thermal energy (kT). This

has been possible due to the lowering of symmetry^{1,2} from $\text{O}_h \rightarrow \text{D}_{4h}$. In octahedral complexes, the singlet state lies above triplet states. As the field along the Z-axis decreases, the triplet state comes closer to the singlet state, thus allowing partial thermal transition resulting in the decrease of magnetic moment.

In the electronic spectrum of the complex (a) three principal bands are observed in the region 9000 cm^{-1} (ν_1), 15000 cm^{-1} (ν_2) and 26500 cm^{-1} (ν_3) whereas the calculated bands are found in the neighbourhood 14955 cm^{-1} (ν_2) and 26545 cm^{-1} (ν_3) showing thereby octahedral symmetry. Further confirmation of O_h symmetry is done by the fact that the ratio ν_2/ν_1 and the value $[(\nu_3 - \nu_2) \text{ calcd} - (\nu_3 - \nu_2) \text{ obs.}]$ are similar to those as observed for octahedral complexes^{4,6}.

In the electronic spectrum of the complex (b) four bands have been observed at 10900 cm^{-1} , 12640 cm^{-1} , 20000 cm^{-1} and 30200 cm^{-1} . The latter two bands are characteristics of an octahedral complex whereas the first two bands may be a consequence of the splitting in the ν_1 band due to low symmetry of the ligand field or it may also be because of the spin-forbidden transition.

Careful examination of the first, third and fourth bands provides following evidences which suggest that it is not a spin-forbidden transition but low symmetry component of the ν_1 band

(i) For O_h symmetry, the calculated and experimental values of ν_2 and ν_3 should be in close agreement^{1,2}. These values are not in agreement for the complex (b), revealing thereby tetragonal distortion of O_h symmetry.

(ii) For d^8 complexes with O_h symmetry, Lever¹³ observed that as $10 D_q$ increases, the configuration interaction between excited state $T_{1g}(F)$ and $T_{1g}(P)$ lowers the ratio ν_2/ν_1 from the theoretical value

1.8~1.5-1.7. However the tetragonal distortion produces E-components of the $T_{1g}(F)$ and T_{2g} levels and the subsequent interaction and repulsion between these levels would cause an increase in the ratio ν_3/ν_1 . This ratio for the (b) complex is 1.83 which is greater than the usual range for octahedral complexes, characterising thereby the complex to be tetragonal.

(iii) The value $[(\nu_3 - \nu_2) \text{ calcd.} - (\nu_3 - \nu_2) \text{ obs.}]$ come out to be 90 (complex-a) and 2790 cm^{-1} (complex-b). The small value confirms O_h symmetry whereas the larger value for complex (b) has been taken as a measure of the tetragonal distortion¹⁴.

(iv) Assuming O_h symmetry, the values of B calculated for these complexes from the diagonal sum rule come out to be 966 and 1166 cm^{-1} . The former value is lesser whilst the latter is greater than the free ion value (1080 cm^{-1}) showing thereby O_h symmetry for the complex (a) and distortion from regular cubic symmetry for the complex (b).

It has, therefore been, concluded that the band at 12640 cm^{-1} is the low symmetry component. Hence for D_{4h} symmetry with H_2O ligands coordinated along Z-axis, the most probable transitions for the first two bands would be ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3E_g$ (10900 cm^{-1}) and ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3B_{2g}$ (12640 cm^{-1}) having energies $10D_q - \frac{3}{2}Dt$ and $10D_q^E$ in terms of radial parameters. The value of parameter Dt, which is directly related to the tetragonal distortion along the Z-axis, has been calculated to be 193 cm^{-1} for the complex (b). It is evident from the calculated values of $D_q(x,y)$, 1264 cm^{-1} and $D_q(z)$, 174 cm^{-1} that the field along the Z-axis is much weaker than along the xy plane, supporting thereby the lowering in the magnetic moment value observed for the complex (b)

Cobalt (II) Complexes

The hexa-co-ordinated complexes of Co(II) ion (d^7) would be high-spin at the weak field limit and low-spin at the strong field, while these states are expected to have comparable stable states somewhere between the two extremes within a comparatively small range of field strength¹⁵. The magnetic moment value for the complex (c) is comparable with that of high-spin octahedral complexes and for the complex (d) it lies in between the values of low and high-spin octahedral cobaltous complexes which may be explained as follows.

The analytical and electronic spectral data do not show the presence of any Co(III) admixed with Co(II). The possibility of the polymeric structure can be ruled out on the basis of conductivity data. For the complex (d), the observed subnormal value of magnetic moment 4.12 B.M. may be because of the presence of lower symmetry component and partial covalent character.

The electronic spectra of complexes (c) and (d) show three bands at 9000, 8300 cm^{-1} [${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F) (\nu_1)$]; 20000, 17350 cm^{-1} [${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F) (\nu_2)$] and 25000, 23650 cm^{-1} [${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(F) (\nu_3)$]. Calculated band positions ν_2 for the complexes (c) and (d) 20900 cm^{-1} and 17560 cm^{-1} show that experimental and calculated bands are comparable for the complex (d) whilst they differ markedly in the case of complex (c). It may be taken as a measure of low symmetry component¹⁶ due to distortion for the complex (d). Using Figgis equations¹⁷ the values of $10D_q$ and B were calculated to be 10530, 9500 and 1097, 786. Thus due to unequal donor strength of H_2O ligand, tetragonal distortion along X-axis is suggested for the complex (d). Agarwal and others^{18,19} have also observed spectra similar to the present complex (d) in case of tetragonally distorted octahedral Co(II) complexes.

The values of nephelauxetic ratio arising out of partial overlap of 3d orbitals with the σ and π orbitals of surrounding donors consist of both $f^2\sigma$ and $f^2\pi$ i.e. $f^2 = f^2\sigma$ and $f^2\pi$ and are 0.98 and 0.81 for the complexes (c) and (d) respectively. The former value is comparable to that of octahedral Co(II) complexes³ whereas the latter value is comparable to that of tetragonally distorted octahedral Co(II) complexes²⁰. The partial covalent character may also be responsible for the subnormal value of magnetic moment in the complex (d) as pointed earlier²¹⁻²².

Infrared spectral studies

In the i.r. spectra of metal chelates the stretching frequencies of azomethine $CH_3C=N$ (1600 cm^{-1}), phenolic-OH (3440 cm^{-1}) and carboxylic -OH (2570 cm^{-1}) groups are lowered and bands around 1490-1550 cm^{-1} , 3350-3400 cm^{-1} and 2490-2500 cm^{-1} appear which show complex formation. This view is supported by the formation of M-N (490-515 cm^{-1}) and M-O (460-478 cm^{-1}) bonds. In the complexes (b) and (d) metal-halogen bond is also formed, it is revealed by the appearance of band around 350 cm^{-1} . The band around 3280 cm^{-1} indicates the presence of unreacted hydroxyl group. Co-ordination of water molecules is indicated by the appearance of bands at 3300 cm^{-1} and 3325 cm^{-1} in the complexes (b) and (d).

Details are given in Table 3.

References

1. K. DEY and K. SEN. *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **52**, 261.
2. R. L. DUTTA and ANJANA BHATTACHARYA. *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **52**, 668.
3. P. SINGH, V. SINGH, B. P. SINGH and R. P. MAHESH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, **13**, 734.
4. P. SINGH, V. SINGH, B. P. SINGH, R. L. GOEL and R. P. MAHESH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **53**, 40.
5. P. SINGH, V. SINGH, B. P. SINGH, R. L. GOEL and R. P. MAHESH, *Curr. Sci.*, 1976, **45**, 187.

- 6 D K RASTOGI and K C SHARMA, *J Inorg Nuclear Chem*, 1974 **36**, 2220
- 7 N S GILL and R S NYHOLM, *J Chem Soc*, 1959 3997
- 8 F A COTTON, *Progress in Inorganic Chemistry*, Vol VI, (Interscience) New York, 1964 p 87
- 9 S L HOLT JR, R J BOUCHARD and R L CARLIN, *J Amer Chem Soc*, 1964 **86**, 519
- 10 W E BULL and L E MOORE, *J Inorg Nuclear Chem*, 1965 **27**, 1341
- 11 S O NYBURG and J S WOOD, *Inorg Chem*, 1964 **3**, 468
- 12 C J BALLHAUSEN and C R HARE *J Am Phys* 1959 **6** 134
- 13 A B P LEVER, *Co-ord Chem Rev*, 1968 **3**, 119
- 14 O BOSTRUP and C K JORGENSEN, *Acta Chem Scand*, 1957, **11** 1223
- 15 X TENABE and S SUGANO, *J Phys Soc Japan*, 1954, **9** 766
- 16 A B P LEVER *Inorg Chem*, 1965, **4**, 1042
- 17 B N FIGGIS, 'Introduction to Ligand fields', JOHN WILEY AND SONS, Inc N Y. 1962
- 18 B SINGH, LAKSHMI and U AGARWAL, *Inorg Chem*, 1969, **8**, 2341
- 19 G R BURS, *Inorg Chem* 1968, **7**, 277
- 20 D K RASTOGI and K C SHARMA, *J Inorg Nuclear Chem*, 1974, **36**, 2225
- 21 R C STAUFER, D H BUSCH and W B HADLEY, *J Amer Chem Soc*, 1961, **83**, 3732
- 22 P E FIGGINS and D H BUSCH *J Amer Chem Soc*, 1960, **82** 820